

Deep-intronic calibration and likelihood-ratio mapping to ACMG evidence strengths

A. Deep-intronic calibration (OOF)

B. PP3 evidence ladder

C. BP4 evidence ladder

● ACMG level reached (stable) × reached (unstable, <5 cells)